

c/o Hotel Naz,

Bandar Abbas,

1/10/71.

Dear David,

Peter Farries brought some sort of verbal message that you were concerned as to my whereabouts. I do not really understand this since I have of course been adhering to the plans I outlined separately in July to yourself and Dr. Naimi, and which I confirmed in my letters of 22/7/71 and 7/9/71, which was precisely on the completion of Yahya to spend two weeks at Minab and then to spend a longer period at Sirjan and Jiruft returning to Shiraz in early or mid October. Having made contact with Peter I shall leave for Sirjan tomorrow.

If you needed more information I wish you could have contacted me. I am I must say extremely hurt and disappointed that you did not afford me the courtesy of informing me of the results of your conversations at the Museum about my permit scheduled for 14/8/. I realise that with the pressures of your own excavation you must have had little time since your arrival from England, but you had promised me both orally and verbally that you would notify me. Certainly no information has reached the Hotel Naz, Yahya before the end of the excavation, nor even when I arrived in Teheran was there clarification! Since then nothing has arrived at Shiraz, neither at the address I gave you in the spring-The I.A.S., nor at the Thoman's house, nor by hand of Andre Singer nor Peter Farries, although I have not since 4 Sept checked on the Asia Institute- a forwarding address which I never gave to Institute to use but which was nevertheless used last spring in disregard of my wishes.

Perhaps you were waiting to speak to me on 24 Sept when I had informed you (in my letter of 22/7) that I would briefly return to Teheran. If so I do wish that you had notified me. I am certainly sorry that I did not arrive on that date (I notified you in my letter of 7/9). I managed to obtain Martha a cheap ticket back to America which could only be used via a connecting flight from Abadan to Europe, so I travelled to Abadan rather than to Teheran, and since I had heard nothing from you I saw no reason to arrange a visit to Teheran which like my last visit would probably find you in Qumis and no message in Teheran.

Please rest assured that my trip to Minab was without mishap. Since I am well known in the area I did not even need the letter from the Museum I had.

I must I fear record a minor change of plans in that because of the early impositions of restrictions on entry and reentry to Shiraz I will arrive there shortly after rather than before the celebrations and will not I expect be able to see you. I would greatly appreciate it if you could leave either with Prof Frye or with Bill Royce some message as to the result of your meetings with the Museum.

As far as I can schedule the next two weeks I leave Sirjan for Jiruft on about ~~the~~ 7 October and will be in Shiraz on 17 October

yours sincerely

Ards